

On the Business Analyst's Responsibilities in an Agile Software Project - a Multi-Method Study

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Abstract

[Context] Agile methods are now used in the majority of software projects, but the definitions of such methods rarely include the role of a business analyst (BA). [Objective] This paper investigates the responsibilities assigned to BAs participating in agile software projects. [Method] We identified potential responsibilities through a systematic literature review (3 databases) and interviews with 6 practitioners. The most commonly mentioned responsibilities were further evaluated in an international questionnaire survey study with 72 respondents. [Results] The combined findings from the SLR and interviews resulted in 89 unique responsibilities grouped into 7 areas. 49 of these were ranked according to the frequency with which they were assigned in the survey respondents' organizations. [Conclusions] Our findings show that BAs typically support Product Owners (rather than taking on that role) and focus on requirements engineering, business needs, and working closely with development teams.

Keywords: business analyst, agile software development, responsibilities, SLR, survey.

1. Introduction

This report provides a full coverage of results on Business Analyst's and Product Owner's responsibilities in Agile projects. It should be considered an appendix to the paper presented at the 32nd International Conference on Information Systems Development (ISD 2024). Due to the limited number of pages only partial findings could be included in the paper.

2. Findings

The findings are divided into 7 work areas, each of them is presented in a separate table.

Table 1. Product Backlog-related responsibilities

ID	Responsibility	SLR: PO	SLR: BA	Interviews
R1	Managing the Product Backlog (PB)	[13], [12], [15], [11], [2], [14], [1], [8], [7]	[5], [6], [9], [4]	A, B, C, E
R2	Accepting User Stories to the PB	[13], [16]	[4]	A
R3	Refining the Product Backlog	[13]	[5], [6], [18],	B, C
R4	Story mapping		[18]	
R5	Prioritizing the Product Backlog			C

Table 2. Requirements-related responsibilities

ID	Responsibility	SLR: PO	SLR: BA	Interviews
R6	Analyzing Use Cases			A, B, D
R7	Gathering requirements	[13], [12], [2], [1], [7]	[4], [18]	A, E
R8	Prioritizing requirements	[15], [14], [1], [8], [7], [16], [17]	[6], [4], [18]	A, B, C
R9	Creating User Stories	[13], [8], [16], [17]	[6], [9], [18]	B, C, D
R10	Documenting requirements	[13], [12], [7]	[9]	A, B, D, E, F
R11	Requirements completion verification	[13], [2], [7]		
R12	Managing Agile sample documentation repository		[6]	
R13	Explaining requirements to developers		[9]	A, B, C, E
R14	Requirements refinement		[9], [18]	A, B, C
R15	Acceptance test criteria definition	[13], [7]	[5], [6], [9], [18]	F
R16	Creating epics	[8]	[9]	B
R17	Designing workshops	[12]	[5]	
R18	Collaboration with stakeholders	[13], [7], [16]	[18]	A, B
R19	Prototyping requirements		[9]	
R20	Analyzing requirements			A
R21	Collaboration with Product Owner on creating requirements			B
R22	Creating UML models			D
R23	Checking if requirements are met			F

Table 3. Project-related responsibilities

ID	Responsibility	SLR: PO	SLR: BA	Interviews
R24	Release management	[13], [15], [2], [14], [1], [16], [3]	[6]	B
R25	Managing the project	[13], [11]		B
R26	Ensuring corporate guidelines and policies	[13], [1], [3]		
R27	Risk assessment	[13], [15], [14], [1], [16], [17], [3]		A, B, C, D
R28	Improving project processes	[13]		
R29	Tracking status of the project		[18]	D, F
R30	Creating specification document			A
R31	Prioritizing tasks			A
R32	Creating project roadmap			B
R33	Organizing other employees' work			D
R34	Adding project tasks to Jira			D, F
R35	Managing Sprints			F

Table 4. Product-related responsibilities

ID	Responsibility	SLR: PO	SLR: BA	Interviews
R36	Maximizing value of the product	[13]		B
R37	Developing product vision	[13], [11], [16], [3], [10]	[18]	A, B, C, D, E, F
R38	Prototyping solutions		[18]	
R39	Critical decision making	[16]		
R40	Being ahead and working on the next product's version			A
R41	Analyzing the product			B
R42	Providing information for managerial decisions about the product			B

Table 5. Business-related responsibilities

ID	Responsibility	SLR: PO	SLR: BA	Interviews
R43	Business plan development	[13], [11], [16], [3]		
R44	Governance management	[13], [16], [3]		
R45	Negotiating with stakeholders	[13], [3]		
R46	Representing the needs of the company	[13], [10]		
R47	Customer relations management	[13], [16], [10]		
R48	User support	[13], [11], [2], [10]		
R49	Providing business expertise	[13], [7]		A, C
R50	Stakeholders management	[13]		
R51	Identifying customers	[10]		F
R52	Travelling to other company sites	[14], [16], [1], [3]		
R53	Advising in political matters	[16]		
R54	Demos assessment	[12], [14]		
R55	Identifying business needs	[11], [2], [1], [7]		A, C, D, E
R56	Improving processes in the company	[11]		
R57	Building trust	[1], [3]		
R58	Communication and sharing vision between stakeholders	[13], [12], [15], [2], [14], [1], [8], [7], [16], [17], [3], [10]	[5], [6], [9], [4], [18]	A, F
R59	Training stakeholders	[16]	[6]	
R60	Finding the best strategy of selling the product			B
R61	Participating in workshops			A
R62	Diagnosing problems or opportunities that could be addressed by the software			B
R63	Proposing the best solution for the particular client			B
R64	Financial analysis			B, D
R65	Market analysis			B
R66	Analyzing business needs			C, D, F
R67	Decision modeling			E

Table 6. Team-related responsibilities

ID	Responsibility	SLR: PO	SLR: BA	Interviews
R68	Sprint Planning involvement	[13], [12]	[6], [4]	B
R69	Cooperation with teams	[13], [12], [10], [16]		A, B, C
R70	Motivating the teams	[13], [14], [10]		
R71	Resolving conflicts	[13], [11]		
R72	Team leadership	[13], [12], [8], [10]	[18]	
R73	Daily meetings participation	[12], [16]	[5]	A, B, D, F
R74	Retrospectives participation		[18]	B
R75	Consultations with team members related to product requirements			A, B, C, D, E, F
R76	Refinement participation			A, B
R77	Participation in demo meetings			A, B
R78	Communication between teams and clients			A, B, D, F
R79	Support for Product Owner			C, E
R80	Technical support for team members			D, F
R81	Performing Scrum Master role			F
R82	Reviews participation - referring goals accomplished, obstacles encountered and future goals			F
R83	Organizing meetings with developers			F

Table 7. Development-related responsibilities

ID	Responsibility	SLR: PO	SLR: BA	Interviews
R84	Designing	[13], [16]		
R85	Implementing	[13]		B, E
R86	Acceptance testing	[13], [7], [16]	[6]	C
R87	Verification testing		[6]	A, B, D, F
R88	Performance testing		[6]	
R89	Merging code changes after passed tests			F

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